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To cite this article: Collazos-Escobar G.A., Gutiérrez-Guzmán N., Váquiro-Herrera H.A. & Amorocho-Cruz C.M. (2020) Water dynamics adsorption properties of dried and roasted cocoa beans (*theobroma cacao* L.), International Journal of Food Properties, 23:1, 434-444, DOI: [10.1080/10942912.2020.1732408](https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2020.1732408)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2020.1732408>

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Published online: 03 Mar 2020.

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Water dynamics adsorption properties of dried and roasted cocoa beans (*Theobroma cacao* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Water adsorption properties are necessary for determining and analyzing water sorption in dried and roasted cocoa beans during storage. Thus, this study aimed to determine the water adsorption isotherms and thermodynamic properties at temperatures of 25, 30, and 40°C and water activities between 0.10 and 0.85 using dynamic dew point method. Thirteen different models were fitted to experimental data to represent the dependence of the equilibrium moisture content. Additionally, the thermodynamic properties were determined using the best-fit isotherm model. The isotherms of dried and roasted cocoa beans showed typical behavior of products rich in soluble components, according to Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) classification, which was satisfactorily modeled using the Iglesias and Chirife and Kuhn equations, respectively. The thermodynamic properties showed that the net isosteric heat of adsorption and the Gibbs free energy decreased with the equilibrium moisture content, indicating the energy changes and spontaneity during the adsorption process. The integral entropy of adsorption indicated the best conditions for product stability during storage.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 30 August 2019

Revised 21 January 2020

Accepted 14 February 2020

KEYWORDS

Spontaneous process; energy released; water activity; equilibrium moisture content; dynamic dew point isotherm

Introduction

Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) has a characteristic and complex chemical composition^[1], is a primary ingredient used in the production of various foods, such as chocolates, beverages, and bakery products^[2], and is one of the primary products exported by some developing countries. Water adsorption isotherms represent the relationship between the equilibrium moisture content and water activity at constant temperature; their knowledge is useful to establish proper storage conditions and to predict the shelf lives of products such as cocoa beans.^[3]

The adsorption process is a phenomenon that occurs on the surface of almost all solids and depends on several factors: the physicochemical properties of the adsorbent, the chemical characteristics of the adsorbates, the prevailing experimental conditions and the affinity between the adsorbent and the adsorbate. The adsorption capacity of the adsorbent can be related to functional groups, verified by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra, which can affect the adsorption efficiency of solids.^[4] Knowledge of the effect of temperature on sorption isotherms is of great importance since foods can be exposed to a wide range of temperatures during storage and processing.^[5] The temperature effect on the sorption isotherms allows determining the thermodynamic properties, which are a fundamental criterion for the prediction of the stability and storage life of dehydrated foods.^[6]

It is essential to understand the hygroscopic properties of dried and dehusked roasted cocoa beans and their dependence on water activity and temperature variations to establish the best storage conditions for guaranteed quality. The present study aimed to determine and analyze the adsorption

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isotherms at different conditions using the dynamic dew point isotherm method (DDI). Moreover, the capacities of different mathematical models for describing the adsorption isotherms and for determining the differential and integral thermodynamic properties were evaluated.

Material and methods

Cocoa samples

Fifteen cocoa samples (*Theobroma cacao* L.) from different farmers of the Huila region of Colombia were processed in December 2018 in the South Colombian Coffee Research Center (CESURCAFÉ): the samples were fermented and sun-dried, and only healthy beans in the same sun-drying processing stage, without any infection or physical damage, were considered for the analysis.^[7]

Roasted cocoa beans

The roasting process was performed at laboratory scale with a TC-150 R rotary system (Quantik, Colombia) at $120 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 ± 3 min. After roasting, the cocoa beans were dehusked manually.

Moisture and composition determination

The dried and roasted samples (5 g) were fully dehydrated in an oven at 105°C for 24 h for determining the dry matter and the moisture content.^[8] The compositions of dried and cocoa samples (water activity, pH, fat content and acidity; Table 1) were determined according to García-Alamilla *et al.*^[8]

Adsorption isotherms

For the development of the dynamic dewpoint method (DDI), 5 g of dried and roasted cocoa beans was placed inside a vapor sorption analyzer (VSA Aqualab Decagon Device, Inc. Pullman, WA, USA). The water activity (a_w) range for the measurements was defined between 0.10 and 0.85 at temperatures of 25, 30, and 40°C , and the a_w interval was 0.01 for the adsorption with an airflow rate of 100 ml min^{-1} . All tests were performed in triplicate for each temperature.

Modeling of adsorption isotherms

The adsorption isotherms were represented mathematically using the thirteen models shown in Table 2, where X_e is the equilibrium moisture content (kg kg^{-1} , dry basis), A is the monolayer moisture content (kg kg^{-1} , d.b.) a_w is the water activity, B and C are the parameters of the modified GAB model, T is the absolute temperature (K), and b_i is the empirical model parameter.

Parameter estimation and statistical analysis

The nonlinear regression analysis used MATLAB® R2019a (The MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA, USA) to identify the model parameters and to calculate the 95% confidence intervals of the parameters. Both the adjusted determination coefficient (R^2_{adj}) and the root mean square error (RMSE) were

Table 1. Composition of dried and roasted cocoa beans.

	Dried cocoa beans	Roasted cocoa beans
Moisture (w.b. %)	5.04 ± 0.72	2.16 ± 0.8
Water activity	0.44 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.04
pH	5.4 ± 0.66	4.6 ± 0.29
Fat Content (%)	43.1 ± 8.6	35.6 ± 6.6
Acidity (mL NaOH g^{-1})	1.8 ± 0.13	4.1 ± 0.33

Table 2. Mathematical models used to represent the isotherms of roasted cocoa beans*.

Model	Mathematical expression	Reference
Modified GAB	$X_e = \frac{AB(C/T)a_w}{[1 - B(a_w)][1 - B(a_w) + B(C/T)a_w]}$	[9]
Oswin	$X_e = b_1 \left(\frac{a_w}{1 - a_w} \right)^{b_2}$	[10]
Halsey	$X_e = \left[\frac{\exp(b_1 - b_2)}{-\ln a_w} \right]^{1/b_3}$	[9]
Smith	$X_e = b_1 + b_2 \ln(1 - a_w)$	[11]
Chung-Pfost	$X_e = b_1 + b_2 \ln(-\ln a_w)$	[11]
Caurie	$X_e = \exp(b_1 + b_2 a_w)$	[12]
Iglesias and Chirife	$X_e = b_1 + b_2 \left(\frac{a_w}{1 - a_w} \right)$	[12]
White and Eiring	$X_e = \frac{1}{(b_1 + b_2 a_w)}$	[12]
Peleg	$X_e = b_0 a_w^{b_1} + b_2 a_w^{b_3}$	[13]
DLP	$X_e = b_0 + b_1 x + b_2 x^2 + b_3 x^3 = \ln(-\ln a_w)$	[13]
Polynomial	$X_e = b_0 + b_1 a_w + b_2 a_w^2 + b_3 a_w^3$	[11]
Kuhn	$X_e = \left(\frac{b_1}{\ln a_w} + b_2 \right)$	[10]
Weibull	$X_e = b_1 + \exp^{b_2(1 - a_w)^{b_3}}$	[14]

*In all cases, a linear dependence of temperature on the b_1 parameter was considered ($b_1 T + b_{1,1}$).^[15]

used as goodness-of-fit statistics. High values of $R^2_{adj} \geq 0.9$ and low values of RMSE (lower than 0.1 kg kg⁻¹ d.b.) are considered to be a reasonable fit.^[6]

ATR-FTIR analysis

For obtained biochemical fingerprints, an FTIR Spectrophotometer (Cary 630, Agilent, EEUU) was used. The ATR-FTIR measurements were performed in a dry atmosphere and at room temperature ($20 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$).^[16] The dried and roasted cocoa beans were ground using a rotating blade and threshed independently; approximately 1 g of each cocoa powder sample was placed in the sampling accessory and pressed. All spectra were recorded within a range of 4000–650 cm⁻¹ with an 8 cm⁻¹ resolution and 20 scans and were submitted to background subtraction. All samples were analyzed in triplicate.

Thermodynamic properties

As the adsorption data of dried and roasted cocoa beans were obtained at different temperatures, it was possible to determine all thermodynamic properties as a function of equilibrium moisture content using the best-fit isotherm model. The net isosteric heat of adsorption (q_{sn}), or differential enthalpy, was computed using the Clausius–Clapeyron equation (Eq. 1).^[17] The Gibbs free energy (ΔG) was defined according to Eq. 2, and the differential entropy of adsorption (ΔS) was calculated using Eq. 3.

$$q_{sn} = -R \left[\frac{\partial(\ln a_w)}{\partial\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} \right]_{X_e} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta G = RT \ln(a_w) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{-q_{sn} - \Delta G}{T} \quad (3)$$

where a_w is the water activity, R is the universal gas constant for water vapor (8.314×10^{-3} kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹), and T is the absolute temperature (K). The integral properties were obtained according

to Tao *et al.*^[18]; the net integral heat (enthalpy) of adsorption (ΔH_{int}) can be estimated with Eq. 4., at a constant potential surface or spreading pressure (π), defined by Eq. 5.

$$\frac{\Delta H_{\text{int}}}{R} = \left[\frac{\partial(\ln a_w)}{\partial\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} \right]_{\pi} \quad (4)$$

$$\pi = \frac{kT}{A_m} \int_0^{a_w} \frac{X_e}{a_w} da_w \quad (5)$$

where k is the Boltzmann's constant ($1.380 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$) and A_m is the area of the water molecule ($1.06 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2$). The integral entropy of adsorption (ΔS_{int}) was obtained using Eq. 6.

$$\Delta S_{\text{int}} = \frac{-\Delta H_{\text{int}} - \Delta G}{T} \quad (6)$$

Results and discussion

Table 3 shows the mathematical models with the best fit results, considering the effect of temperature on the isotherms of adsorption of dried and roasted cocoa beans. It can be seen that the Iglesias and Chirife and Kuhn equations adequately described (high R^2_{adj} , the low RMSE, and statistically significant parameters) the experimental data for dried and roasted cocoa beans, respectively. These equations can be useful to estimate the equilibrium moisture contents in different storage conditions. The modified GAB model did not fit well for dried and roasted cocoa beans; its C parameter was not significant, and the adjusted determination coefficient and the root mean square error were not suitable for representing the adsorption behavior. The statistics of the other mathematical models (Smith and Polynomial) did not evidence good correspondence between experimental and estimated data; hence, they could not be considered to represent the adsorption processes of dried and roasted cocoa beans.

Although the DLP model showed better goodness of fit than the Iglesias and Chirife and Kuhn models for both products, the differences in the statistics were small. These models were selected because they have fewer parameters than the DLP model and they simplify the calculations in the predictions of equilibrium moisture content as a function of water activity and temperature. Moreover, the confidence intervals showed that all parameters of the model were statistically significant at a confidence level of 95%. (Figure 1) illustrates the experimental moisture adsorption behavior of dried and roasted cocoa beans at three different temperatures, as fitted by the Iglesias and Chirife and Kuhn models, respectively.

The resulting DDI isotherms shown for dried and roasted cocoa beans were type III sigmoid-shaped curves according to the BET classification. The type III curve indicated that the sorption behavior was characteristic of products with high sugar and water contents. Similar isotherm forms and equilibrium moisture content values were reported in dried cocoa beans by Herman *et al.*^[19] and in cocoa coatings by Meza *et al.*^[20]; moreover, the authors attributed the trend as representative of most food products rich in soluble components, such as sugars. Other agricultural products with sigmoid-shaped forms include roasted coffee, reported by Baptestini *et al.*^[21]; Oliveira *et al.*^[9], microencapsulated extra virgin olive oil, reported by Bastioğlu *et al.*^[6], spray-dried fat-filled pea protein-based powders, reported by Domian *et al.*^[10], and whole black peppercorns, reported by Yogendrarajah *et al.*^[13]

It is widely accepted that at constant water activity, an increase in temperature causes a decrease in the amount of sorbed water^[10] because the temperature affects the mobility of water molecules and the dynamic equilibrium between the vapor and adsorbed phases.^[13] (Figure 1a) shows the

Table 3. Model parameters and statistical results of dried and roasted cocoa beans.

Model	Dried cocoa beans			Roasted cocoa beans		
	Parameters	Confidence Intervals 95%	RMSE (kg kg ⁻¹ d.b.) R2	Parameters	Confidence Intervals 95%	RMSE (kg kg ⁻¹ d.b.) R2
Smith	b2.1 = 0.169 b2 = -5.986 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.508 b1 = -1.518 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1	[0.148, 0.19] [-6.662 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -5.31 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.485, 0.531] [-1.593 × 10 ⁻³ , -1.443 × 10 ⁻³]	0.95 2.05 × 10 ⁻³	b2.1 = 0.142 b2 = -4.89 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.284 b1 = -8.775 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1	[0.133, 0.151] [-5.172 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -4.607 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.275, 0.294] [-9.082 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -8.517 × 10 ⁻⁴]	0.954 9.089 × 10 ⁻⁴
Iglesias and Chirife	b2.1 = -0.027 b2 = 1.065 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.401 b1 = -1.153 × 10 ⁻³	[-0.032, -0.023] [9.239 × 10 ⁻⁵ , 1.206 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.391, 0.412] [-1.188 × 10 ⁻³ , -1.118 × 10 ⁻³]	0.978 1.355 × 10 ⁻³	b2.1 = -0.049 b2 = 1.705 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.237 b1 = -7.133 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1	[-0.052, -0.047] [1.619 × 10 ⁻⁴ , 1.791 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.231, 0.243] [-7.34 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -6.926 × 10 ⁻⁴]	0.958 8.627 × 10 ⁻⁴
DLP	b3.1 = -0.026 b3 = 7.94 × 10 ⁻⁵ K - 1 b2 = 1.038 × 10 ⁻⁵ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.1 b1 = -3.352 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b0.1 = 0.401	[-0.032, -0.019] [5.735 × 10 ⁻⁵ , 1.014 × 10 ⁻⁴] [8.42 × 10 ⁻⁶ , 1.234 × 10 ⁻⁵] [0.082, 0.118] [-3.949 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -2.754 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.391, 0.411] [-1.175 × 10 ⁻³ , -1.175 × 10 ⁻³]	0.981 1.252 × 10 ⁻³	b3.1 = 0.026 b3 = -8.682 × 10 ⁻⁵ K - 1 b2 = 6.25 × 10 ⁻⁶ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.049 b1 = -1.693 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b0.1 = 0.203	[0.022, 0.03] [-1.011 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -7.252 × 10 ⁻⁵] [4.987 × 10 ⁻⁶ , 7.513 × 10 ⁻⁶] [0.037, 0.06] [-2.064 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -1.321 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.197, 0.209]	0.96 8.352 × 10 ⁻⁴
Polynomial	b3.1 = 4.833 b3 = -0.015 K - 1 b2.1 = -7.253 b2 = 0.023 K - 1 b = 3.09 b1 = -9.876 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1 b = 0.045	[4.346, 5.321] [-0.01676, -0.01356] [-7.879, -6.628] [0.02, 0.025] [2.893, 3.286] [-0.01, -9.233 × 10 ⁻³] [0.044, 0.047]	0.977 1.381 × 10 ⁻³	b3.1 = 0.74 b3 = -2.288 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1 b2.1 = -2.071 b = 6.685 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1 b1.1 = 1.207 b1 = -3.924 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1	[0.425, 1.055] [-3.319 × 10 ⁻³ , -1.256 × 10 ⁻³] [-2.469, -1.672] [5.379 × 10 ⁻³ , 7.99 × 10 ⁻³] [1.084, 1.33] [-4.326 × 10 ⁻³ , -3.521 × 10 ⁻³]	0.948 9.655 × 10 ⁻⁴
Kuhn	b2.1 = 0.414 b2 = -1.201 × 10 ⁻³ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.028 b1 = -1.072 × 10 ⁻⁴	[0.402, 0.427] [-1.242 × 10 ⁻³ , -1.16 × 10 ⁻³] [0.023, 0.032] [-1.214 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -0.039, 0.044] [0.431, 0.53] [-2.322 × 10 ⁶ , 2.996 × 10 ⁶]	0.977 1.391 × 10 ⁻³	b2.1 = 0.257 b2 = -7.838 × 10 ⁻⁴ K - 1 b1.1 = 0.049 b1 = -1.677 × 10 ⁻⁴	[0.25, 0.264] [-8.074 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -7.602 × 10 ⁻⁴] [0.046, 0.051] [-1.761 × 10 ⁻⁴ , -0.014, 0.016] [0.509, 0.596] [-7.205 × 10 ⁵ , 1.068 × 10 ⁶]	0.959 8.59 × 10 ⁻⁴
Modified GAB	A = 0.041 B = 0.481 C = 3.37 × 10 ⁵ K - 1	[0.039, 0.044] [0.431, 0.53] [-2.322 × 10 ⁶ , 2.996 × 10 ⁶]	0.368 7.337 × 10 ⁻³	A = 0.157 B = 0.552 C = 1.738 × 10 ⁵ K - 1	[0.014, 0.016] [0.509, 0.596] [-7.205 × 10 ⁵ , 1.068 × 10 ⁶]	0.459 3.129 × 10 ⁻³

Figure 1. Experimental adsorption isotherms and estimations using the models of iglesias and chirife for dried (a) and kuhn for roasted (b) cocoa beans at 25, 30 and 40°C.

effect of temperature on the adsorption isotherms of dried cocoa beans; an increase in temperature causes a decrease in the equilibrium moisture content at constant water activity, and there were statistically significant differences (95%) from water adsorption isotherms at 25, 30 and 40°C in all ranges of a_w , as confirmed by analysis of variance.

There were statistically significant differences (95%) from water adsorption isotherms of roasted cocoa beans at 25, 30, and 40°C in the range of water activity between 0.1–0.78 (Figure 1b), as confirmed by analysis of variance. However, the adsorption isotherms did not present differences at 0.8 a_w , the value from which a crossing trend was observed, indicating that roasted cocoa beans adsorbed more water at higher temperatures for $a_w > 0.8$. From the range of water activities of 0.1 to 0.8, the equilibrium moisture content of the roasted cocoa beans increased with water activity at a given temperature, and the equilibrium moisture content decreased with the temperature at a given water activity. This behavior has been reported by Akmel *et al.*^[3] in fermented cocoa beans and is typical of many food products. In (Figure 1b), sharp increases in the moisture content at $a_w > 0.5$ at both 30°C and 40°C can be seen. Sormoli and Langrish^[12] reported similar results and attributed this behavior to the dissolution of the sugars in the sorbed water vapor since the food composition affects the moisture sorption capacity. At water activity higher than 0.81, the equilibrium moisture content increased, indicating that the product became more hygroscopic when the temperature increased; this behavior was explained by Eim *et al.*^[5] in carrots due to the dissolution of sugar in the food material. The behavior shown in (Figure 1b) can be explained by chemical transformations during roasting, attributed to Maillard reactions, caramelization of sugars, protein degradation, and synthesis of sulfur compounds.^[8] According to Domian *et al.*^[10], the zone ($a_w > 0.7$) is where the water is available as a solvent for low-molecular-weight solutes, wherein the material probably swells and softens, which is where saccharides dissolve; thus, the water is capable of acting as a solvent. In our case, the effect is notorious in the zone ($a_w > 0.81$). A similar isotherm crossing behavior was reported in dry persimmon leaves by Martínez-Las Heras *et al.*^[22]

(Figure 2) presents the ATR-FTIR spectrum of dried and roasted cocoa beans to relate the results previously presented in (Figure 1) regarding the dissolution of sugar in higher water activities and the water affinity of product compounds. The wavelengths related by the regions 3562–3322 cm⁻¹ can be referring to the phenyl group (attributed to the stretch of O\H), 2925–2854 cm⁻¹ (attributed to the stretch of the C\H of aromatic ring), 1244–1064 cm⁻¹ (attributed to C\H stretch), and 992–680 cm⁻¹ (attributed to angular deformation of C\H of aromatic ring).^[23] (Figure 2) presents similar peaks reported in cocoa from the other cultivars and presents similarity with the FTIR spectra of roasted coffee. Craig *et al.*^[16] reported peaks in wavelengths 2922, 2852, 1743, and 1153 cm⁻¹; the first three bands are associated with lipid absorption, and the last peak has been

Figure 2. Mean average ATR-FTIR spectra of dried and roasted cocoa beans ($n = 15$).

associated with polysaccharides; the region $1130\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is associated with strong carbohydrate absorption, and arabinogalactans may absorb at 1065 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} . Reis *et al.*^[24] reported the content of caffeine in coffee expressed in the wavelength $2922\text{--}2855\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The peaks of absorbance intensity at 1237 , 1013 and 764 cm^{-1} may be associated with saccharose^[25], carbohydrates are in the $1500\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ wavelengths^[26], and the region at approximately 2100 cm^{-1} is associated with carbohydrates and proteins.^[27] According to Meza *et al.*^[20], the presence of fats will influence the food water adsorption capacity due to their hydrophobic or nonpolar nature, as fat mimetics are generally polar water-soluble compounds that facilitate water binding and can alter the hygroscopicity and water adsorption properties of the product.

As shown in (Figure 2), the mean absorbance values of roasted cocoa were higher than dried cocoa in wavelengths between $3000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which could be due to the chemical transformations of dried cocoa beans during the roasted process, thus promoting increases in absorbance values of roasted cocoa ATR-FTIR spectra. Similar trends have been reported by Craig *et al.*^[28] in green (before roasting) and roasted (after roasting) coffee beans. The behavior of the adverse effect of temperature at water activities between $0.81\text{--}0.85$ (Figure 1b) could be explained by the solubility of those carbohydrates and the adsorption affinity of water with the lipids.

For the thermodynamic analysis, (Figure 3a–f) show the estimations of differential properties: the net isosteric heat of adsorption, the Gibbs free energy and the differential entropy of adsorption as a function of the temperature and the equilibrium moisture content of dried and roasted cocoa beans.

The net isosteric heat of adsorption decreased as the water content increased in similar q_{sn} values (Figure 3a,b) and approached zero, indicating that the heat of adsorption was close to the vaporization heat of the water. This property could be related to the adsorption of water in the product and provides relevant information about the energy changes occurring in foods at a specific hydration level, produced by differential changes in the equilibrium moisture content.^[29] Similar trends and q_{sn} values have been reported in green and roasted yerba mate by Červenka *et al.*^[17] The negative values of q_{sn} (Figure 3b) can be explained by the fact that the equilibrium moisture content increased with temperature increases due to solubility of food sugars and not to sorption behavior.^[10] A dependence of differential entropy (ΔS) with the equilibrium moisture content was observed in (Figure 3e,f), showing increases of ΔS with the equilibrium moisture content in dried and roasted

Figure 3. The net isosteric heat of adsorption: dried (a) and roasted (b), gibbs free energy: dried (c) and roasted (d), and differential entropy of adsorption: dried (e) and roasted (f) cocoa beans at 25, 30 and 40°C as a function of the equilibrium moisture content.

cocoa beans. Tao *et al.*^[18] reported similar negative ΔS values in blueberry juice and fruit powders and mentioned that this behavior could probably be attributed to the fact that the food matrix contained more polar groups that can bind water molecules tightly. The negative ΔS trend also has been reported in dry persimmon leaves by Martínez-Las Heras *et al.*^[22]

The negative values of ΔG (Figure 3c,d) indicated that dried and roasted cocoa behavior followed a spontaneous process, wherein the product does not require the addition of energy from the surroundings for the reaction to occur.^[30] ΔG increases with the equilibrium moisture content and temperature for dried cocoa beans in all moisture content ranges, and for roasted cocoa beans, at equilibrium moisture contents up to $0.028 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1} \text{ d.b.}$, indicating that the lower the temperature, the more spontaneous the adsorption process of dried and roasted cocoa beans (Figure 3c,d).^[6] Similar results corresponded with the studies in ground-roasted coffee by Oliveira *et al.*^[9], microencapsulated extra virgin olive oil by Bastioğlu *et al.*^[6], and whole black peppercorns by Yogendrarajah *et al.*^[13] However, the crossing trend of Gibbs free energy with temperature (Figure 3d) at equilibrium moisture contents higher than $0.029 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1} \text{ d.b.}$, corresponding to $a_w > 0.8$, can be explained by the change in sorption properties at high water activities due to the dissolution of sugars in water (endothermic process), which was according to the behavior observed in (Figure 1b).

Regarding integral properties, (Figure 4a–d) show the variations of the integral enthalpy and entropy of adsorption with the water activity of dried and roasted cocoa beans. According to Tao *et al.*^[18], food products should be safely stored in moisture content values with high absolute integral entropy values, as in this zone, the water molecules are highly ordered within the adsorbent and less available to participate in spoilage reactions, which can guarantee the quality attributes of the food matrix.

As shown in (Figure 4b–d) there were decreases of integral entropy (ΔS_{int}) with increases of the equilibrium moisture content, with no temperature dependence with integral entropy adsorption values. For the dried and roasted cocoa beans, the maximum ΔS_{int} values corresponded at the minimal water activity ($0.1 a_w$), indicating the maximum order of water molecules and the highest stability of the product.

Figure 4. The integral enthalpy of adsorption: dried (a) and roasted (c), and the integral entropy of adsorption: dried (b) and roasted (d) cocoa beans at 25, 30, and 40°C as a function of the water activity.

Conclusion

The moisture adsorption behavior of the dried and roasted cocoa beans exhibited type III adsorption isotherms. This behavior is characteristic for products rich in soluble components, such as sugars. The adsorption isotherms of dried and roasted cocoa beans were satisfactorily modeled by the Iglesias and Chirife and Kuhn models, which can be used as tools in the prediction and optimization of storage conditions in a wide range of water activities and temperatures. ATR-FTIR spectra showed that the dried and roasted cocoa beans contained soluble components, such as carbohydrates, and water-affine components, such as lipids and proteins. The roasting process possibly promoted higher absorbance values than were present in the raw material and may be responsible for the crossing isotherms at water activity higher than 0.80, which is thus explained by the possible dissolution of solutes or the interaction effects of sorbate-sorbent. The net isosteric heat of adsorption of the dried and roasted cocoa beans decreased with the moisture content, showing the energy changes within a moisture content range and could be a valuable tool to know the differential enthalpy for a specific hydration level. The Gibbs free energy values evidenced the spontaneity of the water adsorption process. The integral entropy of adsorption allowed the establishment of the idea that the highest stability of dried and roasted cocoa beans during storage could be guaranteed at 0.1 of water activity for all evaluated temperatures.

Acknowledgments

The authors extend their thanks to the South Colombian Coffee Research Center CESURCAFÉ for their support and the FUNDAEMPRESA for providing the samples, which were indispensable to the execution of this study.

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